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Submission of an article to the **PCBS Journal** implies that the work described has not been published previously (except in the form of an abstract or as part of a published lecture or academic thesis), that it is not under consideration for publication elsewhere, that its publication is approved by all authors.

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The manuscript should be on A4 size paper, double spaced using Times New Roman size 12 font, fully justified, with margins of 2 cm and should be arranged in the following order:

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Introduction: Should clearly establish the objectives of the work and its relationship with other works in the same field

Material and Methods: Description of the Material and the Methods used should be brief, and clear enough to make possible the comprehension and the reproducibility of the work.

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Acknowledgements: (optional item)

References: Should be standardized to conform to the requirements of the journal. Preferentially use references that can be accessed by the readers worldwide.

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EDITORIAL

The Pollution Of Science: Plagiarism & Predatory Journal

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We have already noted in a previous editorial that plagiarism is a form of violation copyright, an illegal practice and is considered misconduct research, unethical, perturb and damage the integrity and knowledge of the scientific community. Plagiarism (copy – past) affects all disciplines of sciences and became prevalent in the era of new technologies of communication. Unfortunately these unhealthy and dishonest practices are encouraged by predatory and none reviewed online journals, closing their eyes on plagiarism to "fill" the pages of journals and make a few dollars.

In 2013 we denounced a case of plagiarism, a stupid copy and paste of our article published since 2012 in this journal (PhytoChem & BioSub Journal Vol. 6 N° 2, 83-87, 2012) by another “ scientists” - teaching in Tlemcen and Bechar universities, L. Ziane, H. A. Lazouni, A. Moussaoui, N. Hamidi - and published in Asian Journal of Natural & Applied Sciences, Vol. 2(1), 5-9, 2013 ([www. leena-luna.co.jp](http://www.leena-luna.co.jp)). A journal with editorial board but the editor chief is anonymous.

Due to the complicity of university administrators and predatory journal, the same "authors" return to their unhealthy and disastrous practices. Ziane and al publish an article entitled “flavonoid from methanolic extract of limoniastrum feei (girard) batt (plumbaginaceae)” in *Asian journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research* , Vol 8, Issue 2, 2015, 218-219 (*innovare academics, India*).

The article is an integral copy and paste of our works published since 2010 in Phyto Chem & BioSub Journal Vol. 4 N° 2, 2010 (<http://pcbsj.webs.com/pcbs-j-vol-4-3-2010-2009>), with slightly modification of title and introduction. Unfortunately the editor in chief of this journal (Dr Sharad Jain) made no action or sanctions against this proved stupid plagiarism, it is clear that matching an integral article (Copy and paste) from another scientific journal is a potential plagiarism qualified unjustified attitude, stupid practice and illustrates the potential dangers of the online diffusion of predatory journal.

I think, any one, authors or publisher not condemn and promote these practices should be automatically disqualified from scientific research. The responsibility of editor against plagiarism must be engaged, at least by the retracted of article in question.

Reference:

Cheriti A., 2013, "A stupid plagiarism in the article « Ethnopharmacology and phytochemical screening of bioactive extracts of *Limoniastrum feei* (plombagenaceae) » Asian Journal of Natural & Applied Sciences, Vol. 2(1), 5-9, 2013", *PhytoChem & BioSub, J.*, Vol. 7(3), 88-89.

Fanelli D., 2009, "How many scientists fabricate and falsify research? A systematic review and meta-analysis of survey data". *PLoS ONE*, 4(5): e5738.

Fanga F. C., Steenc R. G., Casadevalld A., 2012, "Misconduct accounts for the majority of retracted scientific publications," *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*, 109(42): 17028.

Macilwain C., 2012, "the time is right to confront misconduct.", *Nature*;488 :7.

Rouajia A., 2012, "La banalisation du plagiat et le triomphe de la médiocrité au sein de l'université algérienne ", *Le Quotidien d'Oran* du 28 février.

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